

ENHANCING THERMAL AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COUNTERTOP EPOXY THROUGH ZrO_2 NANOPARTICLE REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Countertop epoxy is well-regarded for its durability, heat resistance, and seamless finish, making it a favored choice in kitchens, bars, and commercial environments. Its brittleness and limited thermal stability may restrict its use in more demanding environments. This research examines the possible improvement of the performance by incorporating ZrO_2 nanoparticles. Due to their thermal stability and fracture toughness, ZrO_2 nanoparticles have the potential to greatly enhance the properties of epoxy materials. Comprehensive analyses, including Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), tensile, flexural, and impact testing, reveal significant benefits from incorporating ZrO_2 . Notably, it has been observed that 2 % ZrO_2 reinforcement boosts the glass transition temperature (T_g) by 25 %, increasing it from 56 °C to 70 °C, indicating enhanced thermal stability. The best mechanical performance occurs with a 1 % ZrO_2 concentration, resulting in a 70 % improvement in flexural modulus and considerable gains in tensile strength and impact energy absorption. When compared to other nanoparticles like boron nitride and $Mg_2Al(OH)_6(DBS)_nH_2O$, ZrO_2 demonstrates superior performance in terms of glass transition temperature (T_g), flexural strength, and modulus. This makes ZrO_2 -reinforced epoxy an excellent choice for industrial applications, offering a combination of durability, high performance, and aesthetic appeal.

Keywords: Countertop epoxy, ZrO_2 nanoparticles, Flexural and tensile performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Countertop epoxy is renowned for its durability, aesthetic appeal, and thermal stability, making it a popular choice in various applications. However, the growing demand for advanced materials with superior mechanical properties, especially in the automotive and aerospace sectors, has highlighted the need for enhancements [1]. ZrO_2 nanoparticles, known for their high hardness, thermal stability, and resistance to wear and corrosion, are promising additives to improve epoxy performance [1]. While epoxy resins offer excellent adhesion, corrosion resistance, and

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mechanical robustness, their inherent brittleness limits their suitability for high-impact and thermal applications, such as industrial coatings and kitchen countertops [2] .

The National Nanotechnology Initiative (NNI) highlights "beyond nano" as a critical area, emphasizing the importance of integrating nanoscale advancements with larger systems to create functional devices [3, 4]. A key focus is the development of structural laminates using nano-infused polymers. Studies show that polymer-based composites with trace amounts of potent fillers significantly enhance mechanical, thermal, and barrier properties without affecting processability, appearance, density, or aging performance [5]. These improvements, achieved through standard processing methods, are driving applications in the automotive, aerospace, electronics, coatings, and packaging sectors [6] . Zirconium dioxide (ZrO_2) nanoparticles significantly enhance epoxy's mechanical strength, impact resistance, and thermal stability by raising the glass transition temperature (T_g) [7]. This study focuses on developing ZrO_2 -reinforced countertop epoxy, addressing challenges such as nanoparticle dispersion and filler optimization. Properly distributed ZrO_2 nanoparticles improve durability and performance by leveraging their size, shape, and structure [8, 9].

Epoxy resin (EPR) is a thermosetting polymer that has gained significant attention as a reinforcing matrix in polymer nanocomposites due to its exceptional properties. These properties include excellent adhesion, high corrosion resistance, low curing shrinkage, thermal stability, and superior electrical resistance [10, 11]. Nonetheless, the inherent brittleness of EPR significantly limits its application in industries that require high toughness and impact resistance. This brittleness is due to its highly cross-linked molecular structure, which includes rigid components like benzene rings, leading to limited energy absorption and flexibility when under stress. This study aims to enhance those properties of countertop epoxy by reinforcing it with zirconium dioxide (ZrO_2) nanoparticles.

1.1 Material

The countertop epoxy system used in this study consisted of a two-part formulation, comprising Premium FX Poxy Resin A and Hardener B from Countertop Epoxy [12]. The resin (Part A) is a high-quality, clear polymer designed for durable surfaces, while the hardener (Part B) facilitates efficient curing when mixed in a 1:1 volume ratio. Both components are engineered for compatibility, ensuring a smooth, glossy, and highly durable finish surface [13]. Zirconium Dioxide (ZrO_2) nanoparticles procured from Sigma-Aldrich (formally MilliporeSigma). CAS Number: 1314-23-4) were used for reinforcement. These nanoparticles, with a particle size of less than 100 nm and a high surface area ($>25 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), exhibit excellent thermal stability and mechanical reinforcement properties, making them an ideal additive for Countertop epoxy. Their white powder form ensures easy dispersion when mixed into the resin-hardener blend and provide a glossy surface after curing.

1.2 Sample Preparation

1.2.1 Countertop Epoxy Preparation

Countertop epoxy samples were prepared using Premium FX Poxy Faux Rizzle UV+ epoxy resin and hardener in a 1:1 volumetric ratio, following the manufacturer's guidelines. The resin and

hardener were mixed thoroughly in equal parts by volume for 6 minutes, ensuring a homogeneous blend while minimizing air bubble formation by using a desiccator.

The prepared mixture was poured into custom-made silicone molds designed for making tensile, flexural, impact, and thermal analysis samples. These molds, created using 3D-printed anti-molds, using ensured too many times to have precise dimensions and uniformity across all specimens. The 3D printing process enabled customization and seamless mold designs, enhancing specimen accuracy. The samples were then cured at room temperature for 24 hours.

1.2.2 Preparation of ZrO₂-Reinforced Countertop Epoxy

The ZrO₂-reinforced countertop epoxy was prepared by adding varying weight percentages of zirconium dioxide (ZrO₂) nanoparticles (0.1%, 1%, and 2%) to the epoxy resin before the addition of the hardener. The ZrO₂ nanoparticles were dispersed in the resin using hand mixing for 5 minutes. To further enhance the dispersion and reduce agglomeration, the mixture was subjected to ultrasonication with a 10-second on and 20-second off cycle for 60 minutes using a sonicator probe. An ice bath was used to control the temperature and prevent overheating. The mixture was then placed in a vacuum chamber to remove air bubbles. **Although complete elimination of bubbles was not possible, multiple samples were tested, and the results consistently aligned with the manufacturer's specified range for control epoxy, confirming the material's reliability and performance.**

Figure 1. (a) Homogenizing epoxy resin with ZrO₂ nanoparticles using a sonicator, (b) degassing the mixture in a vacuum chamber to remove air bubbles, (c) casting in silicone molds for tensile and impact tests, and (d) curing Samples as neat epoxy or ZrO₂-reinforced.

Following the nanoparticle dispersion, the epoxy hardener was added in a 1:1 ratio by volume, and the mixture was mechanically stirred for 6 minutes to achieve a uniform blend. The mixture was again placed in a vacuum chamber. Once mixed, the ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy was poured into pre-cleaned molds for curing. Similar to the neat epoxy (control), the reinforced samples were cured at room temperature for 24 hours.

For both neat and ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy samples, the molds used for casting the specimens were designed to obtain consistent dimensions for various mechanical and thermal tests. Dogbone-shaped molds were used for tensile testing, bar-shaped molds with V-notches were used for impact tests, and bar-shaped molds were used for flexural tests. DSC was conducted on samples to determine the glass transition temperature (T_g).

The reinforcement levels of 0.1%, 1%, and 2% ZrO₂ were chosen to investigate the effect of nanoparticle loading on the mechanical and thermal properties. These concentrations were intended to assess the performance improvements and identify the optimal concentration for achieving balanced enhancements in strength, toughness, and thermal properties.

2. EXPERIMENTATIONS

2.1 Thermal Analysis Using Differential Scanning Calorimetry

DSC was performed to analyze the thermal transitions of neat and ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy samples, focusing on the glass transition temperature (T_g). The analysis used a DSC Q10 analyzer under a nitrogen atmosphere to prevent oxidative degradation. Approximately 5-10 mg of each sample was weighed and sealed in aluminum pans. The procedure involved equilibration at -70°C, followed by a 5-minute isothermal hold. Samples were then heated at 10°C/min to 250°C to capture thermal events and held isothermally at 250°C for 5 minutes. Cooling back to -70°C at the same rate allowed observation of crystallization temperature. A two-cycle heating and cooling process was used to eliminate residual thermal history.

2.2 Tensile Tests for Mechanical Performance Assessment

The tensile tests were conducted using a Zwick Z050 universal testing machine equipped with a high-precision extensometer (Type: BTC-EXCEL 003) to ensure accurate strain measurements. Type 1 dog bone-shaped specimens were fabricated in accordance with ASTM D638 standards, with dimensions: overall length of 165 mm, gauge length of 25 mm, narrow section width of 13 mm, and thickness of 3.2 mm[14].

Figure 2. Tensile test specimen dimensions as per ASTM D638 [14].

All tests were performed in a controlled laboratory environment at a temperature of $23 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. A uniaxial load was applied at a constant strain rate of 5 mm/min, in compliance with standard testing protocols. The resulting stress-strain curves facilitated the determination of mechanical properties, such as tensile strength (in MPa), strain at break (as a percentage), and Young's modulus (in GPa).

2.3 Flexural Behavior Assessment Using Three-Point Bending

Flexural tests were conducted in accordance with ASTM D790 standards, utilizing a three-point bending configuration. Rectangular specimens, prepared with dimensions of 12.7 mm in width, 3.2 mm in thickness, and a support span of 51.2 mm (16 times the specimen thickness), were

tested. The crosshead speed was approximately 1.28 mm/min [15]. Load-deflection curves obtained during testing enabled the extraction of flexural strength (in MPa), and flexural modulus (in GPa).

Figure 3. Flexural test specimen dimensions as per ASTM D790 [15].

2.4 Impact Toughness Evaluation Using Charpy Impact Testing

The Charpy Impact Test was performed following ASTM D6110 standards to determine the energy absorbed during fracture. Specimens were prepared with standard dimensions: a length of 127 mm, a width of 12.7 mm, and a thickness of 10.16 mm [16]. Each sample was notched as shown in Figure 4. to concentrate stress and minimize plastic deformation during testing.

Figure 4. Impact test specimen dimensions as per ASTM D6110 [16].

The test apparatus was a Tinius Olsen impact tester, which utilizes a pendulum mechanism for the consistent application of impact energy.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Thermal Analysis of Countertop Epoxy and ZrO₂-Reinforced Epoxies

DSC curves of various categories of samples are shown in Figure 5. It is observed in Figure 5 that, for the heating cycle, pure epoxy exhibits a T_g of 56.42 °C, while the addition of ZrO₂ nanoparticles results in T_g values of 63.97 °C, 69.41 °C, and 70.39 °C for 0.1 %, 1 %, and 2 % ZrO₂ reinforcement, respectively.

Figure 5. The glass transition temperature (T_g) for neat epoxy and ZrO_2 -reinforced epoxies.

T_g values for all samples are listed in table 1. The table also indicates the percent gain concerning the control sample due to ZrO_2 reinforcement.

Table 1. Glass Transition Temperature in Heating and Cooling Cycle.

Sample Name	T_g at Heating Cycle	Gain/Loss in %	T_g at Cooling Cycle	Gain/Loss in %
Pure Epoxy* (control)	56.42*	-	59.76*	-
0.1 % ZrO_2 Epoxy	63.97	13	63.09	6
1 % ZrO_2 Epoxy	69.41	23	69.41	16
2 % ZrO_2 Epoxy	70.39	25	70.7	18

Similarly, during the cooling cycle, pure epoxy shows a T_g of 59.76 °C, whereas ZrO_2 -reinforced samples present higher T_g values of 63.09 °C, 69.41 °C, and 70.70 °C for increasing concentrations.

The gain in T_g suggests that ZrO_2 acts as an effective reinforcement agent, increasing the thermal stability of the epoxy. The improvement is most notable for the 2 % ZrO_2 , which demonstrates a consistent increase during both cooling and heating cycles.

3.2 Mechanical Tests

3.2.1 Tensile Test

The tensile properties of countertop epoxy with varying concentrations of ZrO_2 nanoparticles were analyzed, revealing distinct trends in tensile strength and Young's modulus. Neat countertop epoxy

exhibited an average tensile strength of 48 MPa and Young’s modulus of 2.5 GPa. Adding 0.1 % ZrO₂ resulted in the highest improvement, with a tensile strength of 60 MPa (25 % increase) and a Young’s modulus of 3.5 GPa (40 % increase), indicating significant improvement.

Figure 6. Tensile Stress-Strain curves of epoxy varying ZrO₂ content (0.1 %, 1 %, 2 %).

At 1 % ZrO₂, the tensile strength slightly improved to ~52 (8 % increase), while the Young’s modulus reached 3.1 GPa (26 % increase).

Table 2. Tensile Test of epoxy with varying ZrO₂ content (0.1 %, 1 %, 2 %).

Material	Tensile Strength [MPa]	Average	Gain/Loss Strength In [%]	Young's of Modulus [GPa]	Average	Gain/Loss Modulus In [%]
Countertop Epoxy* (control)	50	48±2	-	2.67	2.50±0.20	-
	46			2.23		
	47			2.60		
Countertop Epoxy With 0.1 % ZrO ₂	61	60±3	25	3.82	3.54±0.29	41
	56			3.24		
	62			3.56		
Countertop Epoxy With 1 % ZrO ₂	54	52±4	8	3.26	3.14±0.15	26
	55			3.19		
	47			2.98		
Countertop Epoxy With 2 % ZrO ₂	45	43±2	-10	2.77	2.55±0.21	2
	42			2.36		
	41			2.50		

The reduced gain with 1.0 % concentration compared to 0.1 % ZrO₂ suggests partial agglomeration of nanoparticles, reducing the effectiveness of load transfer within the matrix. A similar trend is observed, with 2 % ZrO₂, a decline in tensile strength to 43 (-10 %), and a marginal increase in Young’s modulus to 2.5 GPa (2 %) observed, likely due to significant nanoparticle agglomeration,

leading to stress concentrations and reduced reinforcement efficiency. These findings highlight that 0.1 % ZrO_2 is the optimal concentration for enhancing both tensile strength and stiffness in countertop epoxy composites.

3.2.2 Flexure Test

The incorporation of ZrO_2 nanoparticles into countertop epoxy significantly improves its flexural properties, as demonstrated by the experimental data.

Figure 7. Stress-Strain curves of epoxy during flexure test with varying ZrO_2 content (0.1 %, 1 %, 2 %).

For neat countertop epoxy, the flexural strength was measured at an average of 54 MPa, with a flexural modulus of 2.5 GPa. Introducing 0.1 % ZrO_2 nanoparticles resulted in a substantial increase in flexural strength to an average of ~75 MPa, representing a 39 % improvement, along with an increase in flexural modulus to 3.3 GPa, corresponding to a 34 % gain. Data from flexural test are shown in Table 3. Again, like a tensile test, the most pronounced improvement was observed with 1 % ZrO_2 reinforcement, where the flexural strength averaged 86 MPa, a 59 % increase compared to the neat epoxy, and the flexural modulus reached 4.2 GPa, reflecting a remarkable 70 % improvement.

Table 3. Flexural test data for countertop epoxy with ZrO_2 nanoparticles.

Material	Flexural Strength [MPa]	Average	Gain/Loss Strength In [%]	Flexural Modulus [GPa]	Average	Gain/Loss Modulus In [%]
Countertop Epoxy* (control)	53	54±2	-	2.46	2.49±0.04	-
	56			2.53		
	53			2.48		
Countertop Epoxy With 0.1% ZrO ₂	84	75±8	39	3.43	3.33±0.10	34
	67			3.31		
	74			3.25		
Countertop Epoxy With 1% ZrO ₂	81	86±6	59	4.12	4.23±0.29	70
	93			4.56		
	83			4.02		
Countertop Epoxy With 2% ZrO ₂	61	61±2	13	3.06	3.04±0.02	22
	59			3.03		
	62			3.02		

However, at 2 % ZrO₂ loading, a reduction in performance was observed, with flexural strength averaging ~61 MPa and flexural modulus decreasing to 3.0 GPa, suggesting potential nanoparticle agglomeration as indicated earlier with tensile tests. Agglomerated particles cause inefficient load transfer at higher concentrations suggested in the reference [17].

3.2.3 Impact Test

The graph shown in Figure 8. showcases the impact test results for countertop epoxy reinforced with varying concentrations of ZrO₂ nanoparticles, revealing a clear trend of achieving enhanced impact resistance with increasing ZrO₂ content.

Figure 8. The impact energy of neat epoxy and ZrO₂-reinforced composites.

The neat epoxy sample exhibits the lowest impact energy of 0.165 J/cm², highlighting its inherent brittleness due to its highly cross-linked structure. Introducing 0.1 % ZrO₂ nanoparticles improves

the impact energy to 0.180 J/cm², while 1 % ZrO₂ further increases it to 0.193 J/cm², demonstrating a progressive trend in the increase of toughness as the nanoparticle's concentration is increased effectively.

Table 4. Impact Testing Results.

Sample Category	Break Energy, J	Charpy Impact Energy, J/Cm ²		Gain/Loss In %
			Average	
Countertop Epoxy* (control)	0.1504	0.15667	0.165±0.016	-
	0.1497	0.15594		
	0.1808	0.18833		
	0.1511	0.15740		
0.1% ZrO ₂ Epoxy	0.1698	0.18258	0.180±0.017	9
	0.187	0.20108		
	0.1642	0.17656		
	0.15	0.16129		
1% ZrO ₂ Epoxy	0.2211	0.22561	0.193±0.025	17
	0.1883	0.19214		
	0.1765	0.18010		
	0.1701	0.17357		
2% ZrO ₂ Epoxy	0.1977	0.22724	0.243±0.026	47
	0.2144	0.24644		
	0.1986	0.22828		
	0.2359	0.27115		

This is due to dissipating energy and improving load transfer within the matrix. The 2 % ZrO₂ sample achieves the highest impact energy of ~0.243 J/cm², marking a 47 % improvement over neat epoxy.

3.3 Comparative Analysis of ZrO₂ and Other Nanoparticles in Epoxy Composites

At the beginning of this study, two other nanoparticles were tried to see how they would affect the thermal behavior. DSC tests were performed and results are shown in Figures 9 and 10. The comparison of glass transition temperatures (T_g) highlights the superior performance of ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy compared to other nanoparticle such as boron nitride (BN) and Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O.

Figure 9. DSC analysis for countertop epoxy with 2 % boron nitride (BN).

BN-reinforced epoxy exhibits the lowest T_g at 45.92°C , indicating limited reinforcement capability and primarily acting as a thermal conductor, which disrupts the polymer network and increases free volume, leading to reduced T_g compared to neat epoxy. $\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_6(\text{DBS})_n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ -reinforced epoxy shows a T_g of 53.57°C , which, while higher than BN-filled epoxy, remains lower than neat epoxy (56.42°C). This reduction in T_g suggests that nanoparticle incorporation introduces free volume, restricts crosslink formation, and alters polymer chain dynamics, leading to a less rigid network [18].

Figure 10. DSC analysis for countertop epoxy with 2 % $\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_6(\text{DBS})_n\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

In contrast, as shown in table 5. ZrO_2 -reinforced epoxy shows the highest T_g improvement, increasing from 56.42°C (neat epoxy) to 70.39°C at 2 % ZrO_2 , demonstrating its exceptional ability to enhance thermal resistance. Some studies have shown that crosslink density plays a crucial role in determining mechanical strength and thermal stability. Generally, a higher crosslink density increases T_g by restricting polymer chain mobility [19, 20]. These findings establish ZrO_2 as the most effective nanoparticle for reinforcing epoxy composites, providing superior thermal stability and durability compared to BN and $\text{Mg}_2\text{Al}(\text{OH})_6(\text{DBS})_n\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Table 5. Comparative DSC Analysis of ZrO_2 and Other Nanoparticles in Epoxy Composites.

Materials	T _g (°C)	Gain/Loss In %
Countertop Epoxy* (control)	56.42*	-
Countertop Epoxy with 2 % ZrO ₂	70.39	25
Countertop Epoxy with 2 % Boron Nitrate	45.92	-19
Countertop Epoxy with 2 % Mg ₂ Al(OH) ₆ (DBS) _n H ₂ O	53.57	-5

The flexural properties of countertop epoxy reinforced with 1 % ZrO₂ and 2 % Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O were also compared, highlighting the superior performance of ZrO₂ as a reinforcing agent.

Figure 11. (a) 1% ZrO₂, (b) 2% Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O with countertop epoxy.

The countertop epoxy with 1 % ZrO₂ demonstrated an average flexural strength of 86 MPa, with individual values reaching as high as 93 MPa. In contrast, the composite reinforced with 2 % Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O achieved an average flexural strength of ~62MPa. These results show that ZrO₂ reinforcement provides a significant 39 % increase in flexural strength compared to Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O. This is attributed to its uniform dispersion and stronger interaction with the epoxy matrix with ZrO₂ nanoparticles.

The flexural modulus further underscores the superior reinforcing capability of ZrO₂ as shown in Table 6. The 1 % ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy exhibited an average flexural modulus of 4.23 GPa, significantly higher than the 1.71 GPa observed for the 2 % Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O composite.

Table 6. Comparative Flexural Test Analysis of ZrO₂ and Other Nanoparticles in Epoxy Composites.

Material	Flexural Strength [MPa]	Average	Flexural Modulus [GPa]	Average
Countertop Epoxy With 1 % ZrO ₂	81	86±6	4.12	4.23±0.29
	93		4.56	
	83		4.02	
Countertop Epoxy With 2 % Mg ₂ Al(OH) ₆ (DBS) _n H ₂ O	66	62±4	1.92	1.71±0.17
	57		1.55	
	65		1.79	
	60		1.60	

The difference in modulus indicates that ZrO₂ nanoparticles enhance stiffness and resistance to deformation under load more effectively than Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O, even at a lower nanoparticle concentration. This improvement can be attributed to the higher intrinsic stiffness of ZrO₂ and its better compatibility with the epoxy matrix.

Overall, the 1 % ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy outperforms the 2 % Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O composite in both flexural strength and modulus, demonstrating its superior capability to improve the mechanical properties of epoxy systems. From Figure 12, the ZrO₂-reinforced epoxy showcases a highly glossy and visually appealing finish, offering a more modern and trendy aesthetic compared to the boron nitride and Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O samples.

Figure 12. Countertop Epoxy With, (a)1% ZrO₂, (b) 2%Boron Nitrate, and (c) 2% Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O.

These findings suggest that ZrO₂ is a more effective nanoparticle reinforcement for enhancing the structural performance of epoxy composites, especially in applications requiring high strength and stiffness.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From our research, we have found out that, the addition of ZrO₂ nanoparticles with countertop epoxy creates a stronger and more durable material. We also found out that by maintaining the optimum concentration of ZrO₂, we can make the countertop epoxy more heat resistant, and

stronger under impact, and that can also enhance flexibility. Through our experiments, we have found out that 0.1 % ZrO₂ works best for tensile strength, while 1 % gives optimal flexural properties and 2 % shows maximum impact resistance. Compared to other additives like boron nitride and Mg₂Al(OH)₆(DBS)_nH₂O, ZrO₂ proves to be the superior choice, making it an excellent option for enhancing the structural performance of epoxy composites. Based on our findings, we hope to open up promising research options like hybrid nanoparticle combinations with ZrO₂ to potentially achieve even better mechanical properties. It is observed that not one single concentration (i.e., 0.1 %, 1.0 % or 2.0 %) gives the best performance for all mechanical and thermal tests. We would like to address this issue by the hybridized approach mentioned above.

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